

April 30, 2023

<https://ijoabs.com/>

Plankton Abundance and Diversity of Eleyele River, Oyo State

Author's Details:

*Oyetunji, O. T¹ and Obikoya, R. T²

⁽¹⁾Department of Forestry, Wildlife and Fisheries, Olabisi Onabanjo University

⁽²⁾Department of Aquaculture and Fisheries Management, University of Ibadan

*Correspondence: tylovang@gmail.com

Received Date: 04-Feb-2023

Accepted Date: 14-Mar-2023

Published Date: 30-Apr-2023

Abstract

The plankton composition and distribution were studied in river Eleyele, Ibadan, Nigeria. The investigation was carried out from November 2010 to April 2011 at five sampling stations and at the surface and 1m depth. Zooplankton comprises of 14 species belonging to 4 families at both the surface and at 1m depth namely; Protozoa, Rotifers, Cladocera and Copepods. Protozoa dominated the population at the surface (74%) and at 1m (88%) depth, *Phacus longi* having the highest overall population of the protozoans. Phytoplankton during the study comprises of 10 species belonging to 3 families at both the surface and at 1m depth namely; Baccillariophyta, Cyanophyta and Chlorophyta. Baccillariophyta dominated the population at the surface (82%) and at 1m (84%) depth, Diatoms having the highest population of the Baccillariophyta at both surface and 1m depth. Phytoplankton and Zooplankton population was highest at the surface (63%, 55%) water level when compared with the population at 1m (37%, 45%) depth.

The Sorenson's index of similarity for both planktons showed similarities during the period of study. The Margalef's index of species diversity showed low diversity in terms of the specie composition during the study especially at 1m depth of the water body.

Key words: Plankton, Margalef's index, Sorenson's index, Eleyele

Introduction

Uttah, et al, (2008) define Planktons as "essentially non-motile organisms relative to the water mass, but drift with it, and are therefore susceptible to pollutants in the water". Planktons are very important in the aquatic ecosystem, they play major roles in nutritional cycles, diatoms and dinoflagellates also serves as basis for primary production. According to Dhanam, et. al., (2016), phytoplankton formed an important source of energy and basis of life in the aquatic environment. Zooplanktons serve as link between the primary producers and secondary consumers like fishes (Ferdous and Muktadir, 2009), Zooplanktons form the second step in the aquatic food chain (Jonah and George, 2019, Brettum and Anderson, 2004). The prevailing environmental variables influence the planktonic communities in terms of their abundance, composition, diversity and seasonal variations (Rothhaupts, 2008), because they respond rapidly to environmental changes. The productivity of a water body is a function of the amount of planktons present in it because they are the major primary and secondary producers (Davies *et al.*, 2009). The study was carried out to investigate the plankton composition and abundance of Eleyele River.

Material and Methods

April 30, 2023

Description of sampling area

Eleyele is a man-made lake, located on latitude $7^{\circ}20' - 7^{\circ}25'N$, longitude $3^{\circ}51' - 3^{\circ}56'E$ and was constructed by Water Corporation of Oyo State in 1939 by damming River Ona within the Ibadan metropolis. The water body is an important resource for fishery, domestic water supply and it is flood controlled with a maximum of 12m during the rains (Olarenwaju *et al*, 2017; Bolaji, 2010).

Field Sampling

Plankton samples were collected at the surface using 53 μ m standard plankton net with a glass bottle attached to the apex of the cone and at the 1m depth using a Kemmerer water sampler. The collected samples were rinsed into a well labelled plastic container and preserved with 4% formalin. The preserved samples were carefully stored away in an upright position for analyses in the laboratory. Samples were collected bi-monthly from November 2010 to April 2011 at five stations in the study area.

Laboratory Analyses

The samples in the laboratory were allowed to stand for 24 hours after which the excess water is decanted to a known volume 20ml. The samples were shaken very well and 1 ml of the sample was taken with a graduated dropping pipette and poured onto a counting chamber and covered with a slide. The prepared slide was viewed under the binocular microscope in the hydrobiology laboratory of the Department of Zoology, University of Ibadan. The species were counted, identified using Maosen, and Yunfang, (1995), Goswani S. C (2004), Jeje and Fernando, (1986) and Wiafe and Frid, (2001).

Biological Indices such as Margalef's index and Sorenson's index were used to evaluate the diversity of plankton and their similarities between sampling sites.

Results and Discussion

Tables 1 and 2 shows the presence of phyto and zooplankton species in the various sites and the Sorenson's similarity index of the sampling sites during the study. Figures 1 to 4 also shows the relative abundance of planktons at both surface and 1m depth.

Table 1: Presence of Zooplanktons (at surface and 1m depth) in the various sites during the study and their Sorenson's index of similarity

Family/Species	Sites 1		Sites 2		Sites 3		Sites 4		Sites 5	
	Surface	1m								
Protozoa										
<i>Phacus spp</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Euglena acus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Peridinium bipes</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Rotifera										
<i>Keratella cochlearis</i>	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	-	+
<i>Brachionus fulcatus</i>	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Lecane spp</i>	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	+
<i>Brachionous calyciflorus</i>	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-
Cladocera										
<i>Daphnia longiremus</i>	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-
<i>Ceriodaphnia spp</i>	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-
<i>Moina micrura</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
Copepoda										
<i>Thermocyclops spp</i>	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+
<i>Cyclops spp</i>	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-

April 30, 2023

<i>Nauplius</i>	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-
Sorenson's index of similarity										
Site 1 vs Site 2										80%
Site 1 vs Site 3										81%
Site 1 vs Site 4										88%
Site 1 vs Site 5										82%
Site 2 vs Site 3										94%
Site 2 vs Site 4										94%
Site 2 vs Site 5										76%
Site 3 vs Site 4										91%
Site 3 vs Site 5										79%
Site 4 vs Site 5										88%

A total number of 939 zooplankton individuals of 14 species belonging to 4 families were gotten from the 5 sampling sites at both the surface and at 1m depth namely; Protozoa, Rotifers, Cladocera and Copepods. Protozoa dominated the population with 264 (74%) at the surface and 390 (88%) at 1m depth, *Phacus spp* having the highest overall population of the protozoans. It has been reported that the presence of a large number of *Phacus* organisms in an aquatic ecosystem is indicative of high organic pollution (Brunn, 2012). Copepod has the second highest population of 125 (13%) at the surface and 4 (5%) at 1m depth. Rotifera with 4 species has a total population of 127 individuals with 101 (11%) at the surface and 26 (6%) at 1m depth. The low number in the population of zooplankton in this study is similar to Brancelj, (2002) in the study conducted on the Slovenian mountain lakes, which reveals that the structures of the pelagic community of the lake shows that Rotifera, Cladocera and Copepoda are presented with few species.

The total population of phytoplankton individuals during the study was 3748 of 10 species belonging to 3 families at both the surface and at 1m depth namely; Bacillariophyta, Cyanophyta and Chlorophyta. Bacillariophyta dominated the population with a total of 3111; 1 949 (82%) at the surface and 1162 (84%) individuals at 1m depth. Diatom having the highest population of the Bacillariophyta at both surface and 1m depth. Mustapha, (2009) also reported in the study conducted on Oyun reservoir on the phytoplankton assemblage that Bacillariophyceae dominated the phytoplankton classes in terms of individual cells/ml and abundance.

Cyanophyta has the second highest population of 617 with the surface water having the majority of 396 (17%) individuals and 221 (15%) at 1m depth, Chlorophyta had 1 specie with a population of 20 (1%) individuals; 16 (1%) at the surface and 4 at 1m depth. The Phytoplankton population was highest at the surface (63%) water level when compared with the population at 1m (37%) depth. This is due to the high rate of light intensity at the surface and below which in turns leads to the high rate of photosynthesis at that level.

The Sorenson's index of similarity for both phytoplankton and zooplankton species between sites showed that there were similarities during the period of study.

Tables 3 and 4 shows the Margalef's index of species diversity for both Phyto and Zoo plankton and it shows low diversity in terms of the specie composition during the study especially at 1m depth of the water body.

Most of the phytoplankton dominant in this study were not considered as harmful and dangerous for human health. However, Harris and Vinobaba, (2012) reported that certain species of *Anabaena*, *Microcystis* etc. are known to produce certain neurotoxin, hepatotoxin and skin damages.

April 30, 2023

Table 2: Presence of Phytoplanktons (at surface and 1m depth) in the various sites during the study and their Sorenson's index of similarity

Family/Species	Sites 1		Sites 2		Sites 3		Sites 4		Sites 5	
	Surface	1m								
Baccilariophyta										
<i>Melosira varians</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Melosira granulate</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>synedra spp</i>	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
<i>Navicula spp</i>	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Diatoma spp</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Cyanophyta										
<i>Anabaena spp</i>	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-
<i>Spirulina spp</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-
<i>Microcystis spp</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Nostoc spp</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Chlorophyta										
<i>Hydrodictyon spp</i>	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
Sorenson's index of similarity										
Site 1 vs Site 2										90%
Site 1 vs Site 3										84%
Site 1 vs Site 4										97%
Site 1 vs Site 5										87%
Site 2 vs Site 3										86%
Site 2 vs Site 4										93%
Site 2 vs Site 5										89%
Site 3 vs Site 4										84%
Site 3 vs Site 5										83%
Site 4 vs Site 5										89%

Table 3: Margalef 's index for Zooplankton

	Surface	1 m depth
Rotifera	0.65	1.00
Protozoa	0.54	0.34
Cladocera	0.59	-
Copepoda	0.39	-

Table 4: Margalef 's index for Phytoplankton

	Surface	1 m depth
Baccilariophyta	0.53	0.57
Cyanophyta	0.50	0.19
Chlorophyta	-	-

April 30, 2023

Figure 1: Relative Abundance of Zooplanktons at the surface level

Figure 2: Relative Abundance of Zooplanktons at 1m depth

Figure 3: Relative Abundance of Phytoplanktons at the surface level

April 30, 2023

Figure 4: Relative Abundance of Phytoplanktons at 1m depth

Conclusion

This study has revealed the composition, abundance and diversity of phyto and Zoo planktons in Eleyele River. The study is important because it can serve as a reference point for further plankton studies on the water body because it has not only revealed plankton compositions at the surface water but also at a depth of 1m below the surface, which is an implication of the extent of light penetration and amount of food as a result of photosynthesis, available at that level and below. Continuous study of planktons is recommended for monitoring of its productivity and evaluating the pollution status of the water body.

References

- i. Bolaji, G. A. (2010). Hydrological Assessment of water resources and Environmental impact on an urban lake: a case study of Eleyele lake catchment, Ibadan, Nigeria. *J Nat. Sci. Engineering Technol.* 9:90-98.
- ii. Brancelj, A. (2002). Fauna: zooplankton, benthos and fish. In Brancelj, A. (ed.), High-mountain Lakes in the Eastern Part of the Julian Alps. ZRC Publishing, Ljubljana: 137–157.
- iii. Brettum, P. and Anderson, T. (2004). The use of phytoplankton as indicators of water quality. NIVA report SNO, 818-2004.
- iv. Brunn, K. (2012). ["Algae can function as indicators of water pollution / WALPA"](#). Nostoca Algae Laboratory. Retrieved 2017-07-25.
- v. Davies, O. A, Abowei, J. F. N. and Otene, B. B. (2009). Seasonal Abundance and Distribution of Plankton of Minichinda Stream, Niger Delta, Nigeria. *American Journal of Scientific Research* 2:20-30.
- vi. Dhanam, S., Sathya, A. and Elayara, B. (2016). Study of physico- chemical parameters and phytoplankton diversity of Ousteri Lake in Punducherry. *World scientific New.* 54:153-164.
- vii. Ferdous, Z. and Muktedir, A. K. M. (2009). A review: Potentiality of zooplankton as bioindicators. *American Journal of Applied Sciences.* 6(10):1818-1819.
- viii. Goswami, S. C. (2004). Zooplankton methodology, collection and identification, Dona Paula,

April 30, 2023

Goa- 403 004:26pp.

- ix. Harris, J. M. and Vinobaba, P. (2012). Impact of water quality on species composition and seasonal fluctuation of planktons of Batticaloa lagoon, Sri Lanka. *J Ecosyst Ecogr* 2.117 doi:10.4172/2157-7625.1000117.
- x. Jeje, C. Y. and Fernando, C. H. (1986). A practical guide to the identification of Nigeria Zooplankton (Cladocera, Copepoda and Rotifera). Kainji Lake Res. Institute 142.
- xi. Jonah, U. E. and George, U. U. (2019). Influence of water quality on zooplankton community of Etim Ekpo River, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *World Rural observation*. 11(3):49- 57.
- xii. Mustapha, M. K. (2009). Phytoplankton assemblage of a small, shallow, tropical African reservoir *Rev. biol. trop* vol.57 n.4
- xiii. Olanrewaju, A. N., Ajani, E. K. and Kareem, O. K. (2017). Physico-Chemical Status of Eleyele Reservoir, Ibadan, Nigeria. *J Aquac Res Development*. 8(9): 512.
- xiv. Rothhaupt, K. O (2008): Plankton population dynamics: food web interactions and abiotic constraints. *Freshwater Biol.*, 45:105-109.
- xv. Uttah, E. C., Uttah, C., Akpan, P. A., Ikpeme, E. M., Ogebeche, J., Usip, L. and Asor, J. (2008). Bio-survey of Plankton as indicators of water quality for recreational activities in Calabar River, Nigeria. *J. Appl. Sci. Environ. Manage.* 12(2) 35–42.
- xvi. Wiafe, G. and Frid, C. L. J. (2001). Marine zooplankton of West Africa (with CDROM). Darwin Initiative Report 5, Ref. 162/7/451, 125p.
- xvii. Yunfang, S. and Maosen, H. (1995). Atlas of Freshwater in China. China Ocean Press, Beijing.373p.